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Finite element modeling of a piezoelectric actuator coupled to the cochlear round window

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Abstract: Round window (RW) stimulation is an application of active middle ear implants. However, its clinical outcomes show a substantial degree of variability due to the mismatch of the diameter of the actuator and the RW membrane, and the surgically challenging for placing the actuator. To address this problem, we developed a new piezoelectric actuator for RW stimulation. Firstly, we specifically designed the actuator's mechanical structure for the RW stimulation. Then, we constructed a finite element (FE) model of the piezoelectric actuator coupled with the human ear's RW membrane. Using this coupled FE model, we studied the influence of the actuator's supporting stiffness and the number of piezoelectric stack layers on the stimulated stapes velocity. Finally, we fabricated the piezoelectric actuator and tested its output on human cadaver temporal bones. The results show that the developed piezoelectric actuator has the advantages of a wide operating frequency range and controlled preload on the RW membrane.

Keywords: Active middle ear implant, round window simulation, piezoelectric actuator, finite element analysis.

1 Introduction

Hearing loss is one of the most common sensory impairments in people, affecting about 430 million people worldwide [1]. The number keeps rising due to the aging of the population.

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Among the patients, more than 90 percent have sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) caused by damage to the inner ear and the loss of the hair cells. The primary clinical intervention for people with mild to moderate SNHL is hearing aids, which improve hearing through their loudspeakers' acoustical stimulation. However, hearing aids have some inherent problems, such as limited high-frequency gain, ear occlusion, and distortions, and 80% patients who could benefit from a hearing aid do not use it [2]. Accordingly, active middle ear implants (AMEIs), which compensate for hearing loss by their implanted actuators' mechanical stimulation, have advanced significantly in the past 25 years [3].

Conventional AMEIs, which have their actuators stimulating the ossicles, require an intact ossicular chain and thus only work for pure sensorineural hearing loss. Whereas many patients with SNHL also have dysfunctional middle ears. To address this issue, Colletti *et al.* implanted the actuator directly on the cochlear round window (RW), bypassing the lesioned ossicles, and got promising results [4]. This RW stimulation extends the indication of the AMEIs from pure SNHL to mixed hearing loss.

Although RW stimulation is successfully applied in clinics, its outcomes vary. The main reasons for the variation are the diameter mismatch between the actuator and the RW membrane [5], as well as the uncontrolled preload applied to the RW membrane during the surgery [6]. To address this issue, a new coupler called the "Hannover Coupler" (HC) was designed and tested in clinics [7]. The HC successfully solves the diameter mismatch problem using a small ball tip and lets the preload under control by adding a spring with a visual indicator at its rear. Nevertheless, temporal bone experimental results show that it still has a poorer response at lower frequencies [8] (125- 1000 Hz), owing to its electromagnetic actuator.

In this paper, considering the piezoelectric stack has the advantage of a wide operating frequency range, we present a new piezoelectric actuator for RW stimulation. Inspired by the Hannover Coupler, we added a coupling rod with a small tip to address the diameter mismatch problem and incorporated a spring with a visual indicator to control its preload. Additionally, a displacement amplifier was introduced to reduce the displacement requirement of the piezo-stack,

thereby decreasing its power consumption. Finite-element (FE) analysis demonstrated that our piezoelectric actuator delivers superior output over a wide frequency range from 100 to 10,000 Hz. This result was also verified in our human cadaveric temporal bone experiment.

2 Structure of the Actuator

The structure of the RW-stimulating AMEIs is illustrated in Figure 1. It includes a microphone, a sound processor, and a piezoelectric actuator. The microphone picks up the external sounds, converting them into electrical signals and transmitting them to the sound processor. The sound processor processes these signals and transmits them to the piezoelectric actuator. The piezoelectric actuator implanted into the RW niche converts the electrical signal into a mechanical vibration. This vibration is delivered directly to the cochlear round window membrane. In the cochlea, the input vibration is detected by the hair cells and perceived as sound.

Figure 1: Schematic of the piezoelectric actuator of the active middle ear implant.

The structure of the piezoelectric actuator is shown in Figure 2. It mainly consists of a coupling rod, piezoelectric stack, displacement amplifier, housing, and supporting spring. A visual indicator was set on the spring to monitor the preload applied to the RW membrane.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the structure of the piezoelectric actuator.

3 Human Ear Model

To facilitate the design of the actuator, a coupled FE model of the actuator and the human ear was constructed, as shown in Figure 3. The human ear portion of this model, which includes the middle ear and the cochlea, was adapted from our previously developed FE model [9]. Specifically, the middle ear in the model comprises the eardrum, the tendons, the ligaments, the ossicles (malleus, incus, stapes), and the joints. The model of the cochlea simplified the cochlea as a straight fluid-filled tube, which is divided into two symmetric chambers by the basilar membrane, corresponding to the scala vestibule and scala tympani, respectively. The apex of these two chambers connects through a hole, representing the helicotrema.

Figure 3: The coupled finite element model of the piezoelectric actuator and the human ear.

4 Coupled Model

In the coupled model, the actuator model includes a coupling rod, displacement amplifier, piezoelectric stack, housing, and supporting spring. The coupling rod and displacement amplifier were made of stainless steel 316L. The corresponding density is 8000 kg/m³, Young's modulus is 193 GPa and Poisson's ratio is 0.285 [10]. The housing was made of biocompatible resin, and the corresponding density is 1100 kg/m³, Young's modulus is 2.4 GPa, and Poisson's ratio is 0.3 [11].

To determine the stiffness of the supporting spring, we analyzed its impact on the actuator's hearing compensation performance using the coupled FE model. During the numerical study, we set the stiffness of the supporting spring to 1 N/mm, 10 N/mm, 100 N/mm, and 200 N/mm, respectively. For comparison, we also calculated the stapes footplate velocity under the eardrum acoustic excitation of 100 dB SPL. As shown in Figure 4, with the increase of the spring's

stiffness, the resonant peak of the stimulated stapes velocity shifts upward, boosting the actuator's high-frequency output. Considering most sensorineural hearing loss is severe at high frequencies, we modified the stiffness of the supporting spring, shifting the resonant frequency of the actuator to 5.15 kHz.

We also studied the influence of the layer number to determine the optimal layer number of the piezo-stack. Using the equivalent stapes velocity under 100 dB SPL eardrum acoustic stimulation as a design standard [12], we set the driving voltage of the actuator to 3 V_P. As shown in Figure 5, the actuator-stimulated stapes velocity boosts with the increase of the layer number. The actuator can stimulate approximately 100 dB SPL eardrum acoustical stimulation when the layer number of the piezoelectric stack is 60. Therefore, we set the layer number of the piezoelectric stack to 60.

Figure 4: Influence of the spring stiffness on the piezoelectric actuator stimulated stapes velocity(K is the stiffness of the spring).

Figure 5: Influence of the piezo-stack's layer number on the piezoelectric actuator stimulated stapes velocity.

5 Cadaveric Experiment

To validate the feasibility of the proposed piezoelectric actuator, we fabricated an actuator prototype, as shown in

Figure 6, and conducted experiments on two fresh human cadaveric temporal bones (TBs). The TBs were obtained from a 52-year-old male donor (left ear: TB1, right ear: TB2). Harvesting and use of the TBs were conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration and approved by the ethics committee of the Beijing Tongren Hospital (approval No. TREC2023-KYS090). For acoustical stimulation, a loudspeaker (ER-2, Etymotic Research Inc., USA) delivered the sound through a speculum inserted into the shortened ear canal, as shown in Figure 7a., as shown in Figure 7a. The stapes velocity was measured by a laser vibrometer (CLV-2534, Polytec, Germany).

For the mechanical stimulation, the piezoelectric actuator was placed within the RW niche, with its coupling rod's tip in contact with the RW membrane and the claw-like structure at the rear of the actuator in contact with the bone wall, ensuring secure placement of the actuator within the RW niche (as shown in Figure 7b). The spring's visual indicator makes a firm contact, the spring experiences a force of 20 mN, thus ensuring that the contact force between the coupling rod and the RW membrane falls within the optimal pressure range for achieving the best hearing compensation performance.

Figure 6: Prototype of the piezoelectric actuator.

Figure 7: Setup for the human cadaveric temporal bone experiment: (a) acoustical stimulation on the eardrum with a loudspeaker; (b) mechanical stimulation on the round window membrane with the piezoelectric actuator.

The experimental results (see Figure 8) show that the cadaveric TBs used in the experiment generally comply with the ASTM F2504-5 standard [13]. Meanwhile, in TB1, the actuator's outputs with a driving voltage of 3 V_P were equivalent to 94, 100, and 120 dB SPL for frequency ranges below 0.6 kHz, from 0.6–3.5 kHz, and above 3.5 kHz,

respectively. In TB2, the actuator's outputs with a driving voltage of 3 V_P were equivalent to 94, 100, and 120 dB SPL for frequency ranges below 0.85 kHz, from 0.85–3.9 kHz, and above 3.9 kHz, respectively.

Figure 8: Stapes velocity under the piezoelectric actuator's mechanical stimulation, and under the 94 dB SPL sound stimulation (ASTM-F2504 is the upper and lower limits produced by a 94-dB SPL sound pressure from the ASTM-F2504-5 standard; TB is temporal bone).

6 Conclusion

We designed a new piezoelectric actuator, consisting primarily of a piezo-stack, displacement amplifier, coupling rod, and supporting spring, to enhance the lower frequency performance of RW stimulation. The preload of the piezoelectric actuator acting on the RW membrane is controllable during the surgery by the visual detector set on the spring. The influence of the actuator's spring stiffness and layer number was investigated by constructing a coupled FE model of the actuator and human ear. Finally, to further verify the feasibility of the proposed piezoelectric actuator, we fabricated its prototype and tested its output by a human cadaveric temporal bone experiment. The results demonstrate that our proposed piezoelectric actuator can generate 94-dB SPL equivalent outcomes over a wide frequency range from 100 to 10 000 Hz and has superior low-frequency performance compared to the floating mass transducer.

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